

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Tourist experience and risk perception on revisit intention: Mediate of destination image

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(01), 2638–2649

Publication history: Received on 16 June 2024; revised on 23 July 2024; accepted on 25 July 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.1.2218>

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to explain the role of destination image in mediating tourists' experiences and risk perceptions on their revisit intention the Royal Sport Horse Bali equestrian tourism destination. The theory used is the Theory of Planned Behavior. This research is a type of quantitative research that is associative in nature. The population in this study were all domestic tourists who had ridden at the Royal Sport Horse Bali at least once. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a sample size of 100 respondents. Respondent data was collected by distributing questionnaires. The data analysis technique in this research uses PLS-based SEM. The research results show that all variables have a significant effect. Destination image acts as a partial mediator in mediating the effect of tourist experience and risk perception on intention to return to the Bali Royal Sport Horse Equestrian Tourism Destination. The results of this research can provide an empirical contribution regarding the effect between the variables of tourist experience, risk perception, destination image and revisit intention for the development of the theory of planned behavior. The management of Royal Sport Horse Bali can implement marketing strategies that highlight the uniqueness and attractiveness of the destination to increase tourists' revisit intention.

Keywords: Revisit Intention; Destination Image; Tourist Experience; Risk Perception

1. Introduction

The image of a destination has a big impact on travel, such as destination choice and future travel intentions. Foroudi et al (2018) who used 6 destination image attributes explained that destination image is the main antecedent of behavioral intentions such as intention to return and intention to recommend. Therefore, it is very important to reinforce a positive image post-visit. Destination image is a key factor that influences future tourist visits. Although it is impossible to control all elements of destination image, tourism actors must build a positive image of tourist destinations.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) explains that consumer behavior is shaped by attitudes, perceived behavioral control and subjective norms that form intentions. Intentions then effect how a person behaves. This theory is the basis for the current study which analyzes the effect of intentions on decision behavior to revisit a destination (Junaedi, 2021). Mayasari and Artini (2021) stated that the revisit intention is a person's revisit intention a tourist destination or the same destination object before. Revisit intention is the intention that visitors have to visit a place within a certain period of time and their willingness to make frequent return visits to that place (Sari and Najmudin, 2021). Tourist destinations are products that cannot stand alone but are a combination product of various attributes that tourists consider when making decisions to visit or revisit. With the large number of tourist visits, tourism will continue to develop and maintain tourists' desire to revisit (Rismawati and Sitepu, 2021).

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Revisit intention is something that is related to consumer behavior after a visit. It is important to study this to find out how customers return to visit and retain customers. Revisit intention can be defined as the act of revisiting the same tourist destination in the future as a direct impact of post-visit behavior within a certain period of time. Stylos et al., (2016) stated that in applying the marketing management concept, businesses need to pay attention to consumer behavior and the factors that effect purchasing decisions in their product or service marketing efforts. This is one way to be more effective and efficient in understanding consumer needs and desires, as well as providing the expected satisfaction, compared to competitors (Kotler and Keller, 2016).

Destination image is one of the considerations for tourists who want to visit a tourist attraction. If a tourist attraction has a good image, it will effect the visiting intentions of tourists who want to visit a destination. Image can be interpreted as the public's perception of the identity of a company or association. Destination image can be formed into a strong motivating factor or driver of tourist travel to a tourist destination. According to Chi & Qu (2008), stated that destination image can effect tourist behavior in the future.

Fadiryana and Chan (2019) stated that tourist experience is the experience gained by tourists, both directly and indirectly, regarding the service process, management of facilities, and how a tourist interacts with the manager and with other tourists. The tourist experience begins before arrival at a destination and ends with memories of the experience and planning to visit in the future (Prakoso et al, 2020). Satisfied or dissatisfied tourist experiences only indicate whether tourist expectations are met or not (Lim et al, 2021).

Apart from tourists' experiences, tourists' risk perceptions also have an impact on tourists' travel behavior and their revisit intention a destination in the future. According to Abraham et al (2020) the choice of tourist destination can be influenced by perceptions of risk, where tourists tend to choose tourism with low risk. For tourists, perceived risk not only influences the intention to seek information before purchasing but also the purchasing process and decisions after purchase. Based on a tourism perspective, if the amount of risk involved in visiting a destination is high, people will tend to avoid places they consider unsafe. Tourist behavior in the process of selecting a tourist destination is determined by various factors. One of them is perceived risk and destination image is considered an important component. Thus, understanding tourist behavior requires a better understanding of tourists' perceptions of risk and place image to facilitate effective marketing strategies (Hsu and Kang, 2018). According to the research results of Anugrah and Mahendra, (2021), tourists' risk perceptions have a significant but negative effect on their revisit intention.

A positive destination image can help reduce tourists' concerns about potential risks and vice versa. It is believed that a low risk perception will be able to provide a positive destination image and increase tourists' revisit intention. On the other hand, the perception and image of a destination can effect tourists' intentions to return to a destination. This is related to the destination's ability to provide a good and unforgettable experience during travel (Darajat et al, 2021). Kozak et al. (2007) suggested that tourists' perceptions of the physical risk of disasters and destination image are very likely to play an important role in influencing tourists' intentions to revisit. This is supported by Lepp et al. (2011) by combining risk and image to understand the cognitive and affective processes that individuals experience when they feel threatened.

According to Mayasari and Artini (2021) tourist experience has a significant effect on revisit intention. There is a significant effect between tourist experience on revisit intention because when tourists want to decide on a destination plan, they rely on previous impressive experiences they have had. The research results of Nugraha et al (2021) state that tourists' experiences during a visit to a tourist destination effect tourists' intention to make a repeat visit. This is because tourist activities that are actively participated in by tourists will form an experience as an intrinsic encouragement for tourists which motivates tourists to make repeat visits to a tourist destination.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Tourist experience is the feeling or emotion that tourists feel after enjoying a tourist destination (Pujiastuti, 2020). A positive experience will ensure consumers always have a comfortable and safe atmosphere. This will have an impact on consumers' intentions to make repeat purchases (Saraswathi and Wardana, 2021). In the context of tourism, a satisfying travel experience will increase the desire to use the same object in the future (Hasan, 2015). The results of previous research conducted by Zhang et al. (2018) memorable tourism experiences have a positive effect on revisit intention. Research conducted by Napitupulu et al. (2021) stated that visiting experience has a significant positive effect on revisit intention. There is a positive and significant effect of the demand for an unforgettable travel experience on the revisit intention. This means that the more memorable the tourist experience is felt by tourists, the greater the tourist's revisit intention (Noerhanifati et al. 2020). The results of previous research conducted by Yoo et al. (2020) stated that customer experience can effect return visit intentions positively and significantly. The same research results were also found by

Primananda, et al (2022) that experience has a significant effect on revisit intention. Tourists' motivation for visiting tours is to gain new experiences, vacation with family and escape from routine work.

H1: Tourist experience has a positive and significant effect on revisit intention

Peter and Olson (2012) stated that perceived risk is an unintended consequence that consumers want to avoid when purchasing and using a product or service. Research (Cong, 2021) states that perceived risk has a significant effect on revisit intention. In addition, (Noh and Vogt, 2013) argue that knowledge about destinations can reduce tourists' uncertainty in choosing a holiday location. A positive risk perception will increase the intention or desire to visit a place repeatedly. Likewise, Chew and Jahari's (2014) research with Malaysian tourists who had visited Japan previously concluded that only perceived physical risk influenced their revisit intention. The empirical findings of Artuğer's (2015) study show that psychological risks, time risks, physical risks, financial risks and performance risks are felt by foreign tourists during holidays. Mayasari's research results (2021) show that perceived risk does not have a significant effect on revisit intention on virtual educational tourism at the Surabaya Zoo. The occurrence of the Covid-19 pandemic apparently has not dampened someone's intention to visit a tourist destination. Current technological advances mean that they can still carry out tourism activities even virtually without having to visit tourist attractions in person.

H2: Perception of risk has a negative and significant effect on revisit intention.

Experience can also effect an individual's perception of the image of a destination. Through the quality of experience, it can shape perceptions about the tourist destinations that have been visited. The quality of experience can effect the destination image, where the destination image is a complex combination of products, services and attributes that are woven into a total impression (Tan, 2016). Wong and Lai (2021) stated that non-game memorable tourism experiences have a strong impact on destination image. The results of research conducted by Pradyka (2018) showed that the quality of experience significantly influences the destination image. Noerhanifati's (2020) research states that there is a positive and significant effect between the image of a tourist destination and an unforgettable travel experience. This means that the higher the tourist perception of the image of the tourist destination, the more positive the tourist experience will be felt by tourists.

H3: Tourist experience has a positive and significant effect on destination image.

Loureiro and Jesus (2019) stated that the perception of risky events can manifest negative cognitive associations (negative thoughts), unpleasant emotional states and not considering the destination as a potential place of travel and not wanting to repeat the experience. Thus, risk perception can effect destination image assessment. According to Sitio's research results (2020), Physical Risk Perception has a negative and significant effect on destination image, and Psychological Risk Perception has no effect on destination image. In Rinandiyana's (2022) research, in the current pandemic era, the image of a tourist spot is no longer only built on its attractiveness, but also on the guarantee that the place is able to provide security from risks.

H4: Perception of risk has a negative and significant effect on destination image.

Kim (2017) stated that several literatures related to destination image have been identified and there is a direct and indirect effect on behavioral intentions. In other research, it was stated that destination image directly influences tourists' intentions to revisit tourists in the future and their willingness to recommend tourist destinations to others. In line with research conducted by Napitupulu et al. (2021) which states that destination image has a positive effect on revisit intention. Noerhanifati et al. (2020) also stated that destination image has a positive effect on the intensity of return visits. Hidayat et al. (2017) stated that destination image has a significant effect on revisit intention and Fatimah (2019) also stated that destination image has a positive and significant effect on revisit intention. Main research results (2020) state that the destination image variable has a significant positive effect on tourists' revisit intention.

H5: Destination image has a positive and significant effect on revisit intention.

Yin et al. (2014) found that travel satisfaction is one of the most important variables that mediates and influences tourists' intention to visit directly, besides that they also found that the effect of destination image influences revisit intention. If the quality of experience felt and obtained during a tourist visit presents a positive impression, then this can create a positive image in the minds of visitors regarding the destination visited. Research conducted by Pradyka (2018) shows that destination image is able to partially mediate the effect of experience quality on revisit intention. Tamahela's (2020) research results state that visitor experiences have a positive effect on the decision to revisit the Mojosemi Forest Park Magetan tourist attraction. Artha's research (2020) states that simultaneously, destination image

and visiting experience have a significant effect on intention to return to the Tangkuban Perahu tourist attraction. Noerhanifati's (2020) research states that there is a positive and significant effect on the image of a tourist destination on the revisit intention through an unforgettable travel experience. This means that the higher the image of a tourist destination and the unforgettable travel experience a student has, the greater the tourist's revisit intention.

H6: Destination image can mediate the effect between tourist experience and revisit intention.

Research (Chew and Jahari, 2014) used destination image as a mediator between perceived risk and revisit intention, and found that destination image had a significant effect on revisit intention. The results obtained from Martinayanti's (2016) research are that risk perception has a negative and significant effect on the intention to purchase fashion products via Instagram. The results of descriptive analysis in Darajat's research (2021) show that the image created by Anyer Beach is good because this has an impact on the revisit intention even though there is a perceived risk. According to the research results of Sitio (2020), the destination image variable partially mediates the effect (partial mediation) between physical risk perception and revisit intention and the destination image variable does not mediate the effect (no mediation) between Psychological Risk Perception and revisit intention. Destination image is also known to mediate the effect between risk perception and revisit intention. This shows that high risk perception can be mediated by a strong destination image, so that tourists remain willing to return to Pangandaran Beach in the future (Wulandari, 2023). The research results of Wulandari and Annisa (2020) state that destination image can mediate the effect of risk perception on revisit intention.

H7: Destination image can mediate the effect between risk perception and revisit intention.

3. Methods

This research uses an associative quantitative approach. The associative approach is research that aims to determine the effect between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2018:57). This approach is used to analyze the effect between tourist experience variables on revisit intention through destination image and the effect between risk perception variables on revisit intention through destination image.

The population in this study were all tourists who had visited the Royal Sport Horse Bali. This population number cannot be stated or calculated with certainty (infinite) because the data cannot be known with certainty. The sampling method used is non-probability sampling, namely a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. Inferential statistical analysis is a statistical calculation that helps researchers to draw conclusions about the population (Rahyuda, 2020:317). The inferential statistics used are SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis based on PLS (Partial Least Square).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Evaluation of the Structural Model or Inner Model

4.1.1. *Inner model analysis is a structural model that ensures that the structural model is strong and accurate.*

R-Square

The R-Square (R²) value calculation aims to see how large the correlation value of the endogenous variables is resulting from the PLS estimation of each path (Hair et al., 2017: 213). The R-square (R²) value ranges from 0 to 1, with the assumption that the higher the R-square value, the better the research structural model. The results of the R-square value can be seen in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1 R-square

Variable	R Square
Citra Destinasi	0.842
Niat Berkunjung Kembali	0.890

Primary Data, 2024

Based on Table 1, it shows that the R-square value of the Destination Image variable is 0.842. This means that 84 percent of the variability in the Destination Image construct can be explained by tourist experience and risk perception variables, while the remaining 16 percent of the destination image variable is explained by other variables outside the model. Likewise, the variable intention to return to visit has an R-square value of 0.890. This means that 89 percent of the variability in the revisit intention construct can be explained by the variables of tourist experience, risk perception, and destination image, while the remaining 11 percent of the revisit intention variable is explained by other variables outside the model.

Q-Square predictive relevance

The aim of calculating the Q-Square predictive relevance value is to measure the value of observations produced by the model and estimate model parameters. According to Hair et al (2017:222), a Q-square (Q^2) value > 0 means that the exogenous construct has predictive relevance to the endogenous construct, whereas if the Q^2 value ≤ 0 means the model lacks predictive relevance. The Q^2 value has a value interval between $0 < Q^2 < 1$, with the Q^2 value getting closer to 1 indicating that the model is getting better. The Q^2 value is determined based on the Cross Validated Redundancy value in SEM PLS, because in this approach there is a process of including important elements from the path model and model structure to predict omitted data points. Model of the effect of tourist experience, risk perception and destination image on visiting intentions again gives the R-square value as listed in table 5.13, then the Q-Square predictive relevance value can be seen as follows $Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) (1 - R^2_2)$

$$= 1 - (1-0,842) (1-0,890)$$

$$= 1 - (0,158) (0,110)$$

$$= 1 - 0,017$$

$$= 0,983$$

The Q^2 calculation result is 0.983, so the conclusion is that the revisit intention the Royal Sport Horse Bali Equestrian Tourism Destination in this study has a relevant predictive value of 98.3% because it can explain the information in this study and is classified as very strong.

Goodness of Fit

This GoF value is obtained from the square root of multiplying the average average variance extracted (AVE) value with the average R-square value (R^2). The GoF criteria are in the value range 0 – 1 with value interpretations namely 0.1 (small GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.36 (large GoF). The following is the Goodness of Fit calculation in structural model testing.

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$\overline{AVE} = \text{rata-rata AVE} = 0,758$$

$$\overline{R^2} = \text{rata-rata } R^2 = 0,866$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{\overline{AVE} \times \overline{R^2}}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,758 \times 0,866}$$

$$GoF = 0,810$$

Based on the results of these calculations, a GoF value of 0.810 is obtained, which means that the research model already has a large GoF value. This value influences the goodness of the structural model in this research. Overall testing of the structural model (inner model) obtained good results, so it can be concluded that this structural model is declared good and is able to provide predictive power for the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables in this research.

4.2. Direct Effect

The statistical test used to carry out hypothesis testing is the t test. The following are the results of the direct effect test using bootstrapping in PLS analysis.

Table 2 Direct Effect

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
Tourist experience -> Revisit intention	0.396	0.392	0.084	4.709	0.000	Significant
Risk perception -> Revisit intention	-0.094	-0.096	0.047	2.016	0.046	Significant
Tourist experience -> Destination image	0.833	0.835	0.039	21.319	0.000	Significant
Risk perception -> Destination image	-0.145	-0.140	0.044	3.299	0.001	Significant
Destination image -> Revisit intention	0.511	0.513	0.084	6.046	0.000	Significant

Primary Data, 2024

4.2.1. Tourist experience on revisit intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of tourist experience on revisit intention produced an original sample value of 0.396, which shows a positive number, so it can be said that tourist experience on revisit intention has a positive effect. The t-statistic value is $4.709 > t\text{-table (1.96)}$ and Pvalues $0.000 < \alpha (0.05)$, these results indicate that tourist experience has a significant positive effect on revisit intention or H1 can be accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the tourist experience variable, the value of the revisit intention variable also increases significantly.

4.2.2. Risk perception on revisit intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of risk perception on intention to return visit produced an original sample value of -0.094, which shows a negative number, so it can be said that risk perception on intention to return visit has a negative effect. The t-statistic value of $2.016 > t\text{-table (1.96)}$ and P value of $0.046 < 0.05$ indicate that risk perception has a significant negative effect on the revisit intention the Royal Sport Horse Bali Equestrian Tourism Destination so that H2 is accepted.

4.2.3. Tourist experience on destination image

The results of the effect of tourist experience on destination image produced an original sample value of 0.833, which shows a positive number, so it can be said that tourist experience on destination image has a positive effect. The t-statistic value is $21.319 > t\text{-table (1.96)}$ and Pvalues $0.000 < \alpha (0.05)$, these results indicate that tourist experience has a significant positive effect on destination image or H3 is acceptable. This result also means that the higher the value of the tourist experience variable, the value of the destination image variable also increases significantly.

4.2.4. Risk perception on destination image

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of risk perception on destination image produce an original sample value of -0.145, which shows a negative number, so it can be said that risk perception on destination image has a negative effect. The t-statistic value of $3.299 > t\text{-table (1.96)}$ and P value of $0.001 < 0.05$ indicate that risk perception has a significant negative effect on the destination image at the Royal Sport Horse Bali Equestrian Tourism Destination so that H4 is accepted.

4.2.5. Destination image on revisit intention

The results of the effect of destination image on revisit intention produced an original sample value of 0.511, which shows a positive number, so it can be said that destination image has a positive effect on intention to return visit. The t-

statistic value is $6.046 > t\text{-table} (1.96)$ and $P\text{values } 0.000 < \alpha (0.05)$, these results indicate that destination image has a significant positive effect on revisit intention or $H5$ can be accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the destination image variable, the value of the revisit intention variable also increases significantly.

4.3. Indirect Effect

Testing the indirect effect or mediating variables in this research refers to the role of destination image in mediating the effect of tourist experience and risk perception on revisit intention. The mediating variable has a positive and significant effect when the t statistic value $> t$ table and p value $<$ significance value or $\alpha 0.05$. The following are the results of tests of indirect effects or mediating variables in PLS analysis.

Table 3 Indirect Effect

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
Tourist experience -> Destination image -> Revisit intention	0.425	0.428	0.070	6.040	0.000	Significant
Risk perception -> Destination image -> Revisit intention	-0.074	-0.073	0.028	2.631	0.010	Significant

Primary Data, 2024

4.3.1. Tourist experience on revisit intention mediated by destination image

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the results of the effect of tourist experience on revisit intention through destination image as mediation produce an original sample value of 0.425 which shows a positive number, so it can be said that tourist experience on revisit intention through destination image as mediation has a positive effect. The t -statistic value is $6.040 > t\text{-table} (1.96)$ and $P\text{values } 0.000 < \alpha (0.05)$, these results indicate that tourist experience has a significant positive effect on revisit intention or $H6$ can be accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the tourist experience variable, the value of the intention to return visit variable through destination image also increases significantly.

4.3.2. Risk perception on revisit intention with the mediation of destination image

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the results of the effect of risk perception on revisit intention through destination image as mediation produce an original sample value of -0.074, which shows a negative number, so it can be said that risk perception on revisit intention through destination image as mediation has a negative effect. The t -statistic value of $2.631 > t\text{-table} (1.96)$ and $P\text{values } 0.010 < 0.05$ indicate that risk perception has a significant negative effect on revisit intention through destination image as mediation so that $H7$ is accepted. This means that the higher the value of the risk perception variable, the revisit intention through the destination image will decrease significantly.

5. Conclusion

Tourist experience, risk perception can effect the image of the destination and can effect the revisit intention. The results of mediation testing in this research also obtained empirical evidence which states that destination image can mediate the effect of tourist experience, risk perception on revisit intention. Besides that, the theoretical implications of this research provide evidence that the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is related to consumer behavior formed by attitudes, perceived behavioral control and subjective norms that shape intentions. Intentions then effect how a person behaves. With this theory as the basis for the current study, we can analyze the effect of intentions on decision behavior to revisit a destination.

5.1. Managerial Implications

It is hoped that the practical implications of this research can become material for consideration and input for equestrian tourism destinations, especially Royal Sport Horse Bali, in increasing intentions to return to the destination. It is hoped that the results of this research can help destination managers in developing more effective marketing

strategies to increase tourists' revisit intention. Destination managers can focus on strengthening the positive image of the destination, improving the tourist experience, and reducing the risk perception that potential visitors may have.

It is hoped that this research will provide consideration for destination managers in taking concrete steps to improve the services, facilities and activities offered to visitors. In addition to managing the risks associated with tourist visits. By better understanding travelers' risk perceptions, they can identify areas where those risks can be reduced or better managed to increase visitor confidence and safety.

The implications of this research can also lead to the development of training programs for staff and employees who work at Royal Sport Horse Bali. They can be trained to provide a more satisfying tourist experience and build a positive image of the destination through positive interactions with visitors. In addition, the results of this research can be used as a basis for measuring destination performance in attracting and retaining tourists. Destination managers can use the indicators identified in the research to monitor their performance over time and make necessary strategic adjustments.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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